

Analysis of Zero Inflated Poisson Regression Model with A New Modified Bias Estimator on Tetanus Neonatorum Data in Bandar Lampung

Amanda Faza Fahirani¹, Netti Herawati^{1*}, Dorrah Azis¹, dan Nusyirwan¹

¹Department of Mathematics, University of Lampung, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia

Received: 18.03.2025 | Accepted: 21.03.2025 | Published: 25.03.2025

*Corresponding Author: Netti Herawati¹

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15079402](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15079402)

Abstract

Case Studies

In Poisson Regression, assuming that the variant value must be equal to the mean (equidispersion), then another alternative is used for data that has a variant value greater than the mean (overdispersion). Overdispersion in Poisson regression can be overcome by using the Zero Inflated Poisson model. The purpose of this study is to model Zero Inflated Poisson (ZIP) with New Modified Bias Estimator in cases of Tetanus Neonatorum in Bandar Lampung, Indonesia. In addition, this study also compares the performance of Zero Inflated Poisson with new modified bias estimator with Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) method in handling multicollinearity and overdispersion in application data. The best model based on the smallest Mean Squared Error (MSE) value. The results of the study indicate that the Zero Inflated Poisson model with a new modified bias estimator is better in modeling Tetanus Neonatorum case data in Bandar Lampung, Indonesia because it has a smaller MSE value (0.8819) than the MLE (75.5678). The Zero Inflated Poisson model with a new modified bias estimator shows that Tetanus Neonatorum in Bandar Lampung, Indonesia is influenced by the percentage of pregnant women examined (X_1) and the percentage of neonatal examination (X_4).

Keywords: *Multicollinearity, Overdispersion, Poisson Regression, Ridge Estimators, Zero Inflated Poisson Regression*

1. INTRODUCTION

Poisson regression is used to describe the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable which is Poisson distributed. Sometimes, the data used violate the multicollinearity assumption, leading to the failure of one of the classical assumptions and resulting in parameter estimates with non-minimum variance. Therefore, the Poisson Ridge Regression (PPR) method is needed to address this issue [4]. In the Poisson regression model, there is an assumption that must be met, namely that the variance value must be equal to the mean (equidispersion). However, there is another alternative if data is found with a variance value greater than the mean, known as overdispersion. Overdispersion occurs when the variance of the response variable is greater than what is predicted by the model, which can be caused by several factors. These factors include unobserved

heterogeneity, dependency between events, the presence of outliers, and an excess number of zeros in the dependent variable [3]. This problem can be overcome by using the Zero Inflated Poisson (ZIP) method. In many cases, the Poisson distribution model is unable to handle a high proportion of zeros or the variability of computational data that does not conform to the assumptions of the Poisson distribution. The Zero Inflated Poisson model offers better adjustability in capturing excess zeros in a more effective way resulting in better model accuracy, especially in situations where excess zeros have a significant impact on the data distribution [7]. In dealing with data that has multicollinearity and overdispersion problems, the Zero Inflated Poisson method can be used with several modified bias estimator values of Ridge k (k_1 , k_2 , and k_3). This research will model Zero Inflated Poisson on Tetanus Neonatorum cases in Bandar Lampung City, Lampung and compare which method is better

between Zero Inflated Poisson with the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) method and several modified bias estimator values of Ridge k (k_1 , k_2 , and k_3) based on the smallest Mean Squared Error (MSE) value. There are several previous studies that have discussed the problem of data experiencing overdispersion and multicollinearity, such as research on Positive Malaria Disease Data in East Java, Indonesia using the Zero Inflated Poisson method to overcome the problem of overdispersion in the data [1] and research using a new modified estimator on the Zero Inflated Poisson regression model using simulated data to overcome overdispersion and multicollinearity problems in simulated data [7]. Based on this, the author is interested in conducting research using the Zero Inflated Poisson method with new modified estimates in overcoming overdispersion and

multicollinearity problems in Tetanus Neonatorum disease data in Bandar Lampung City, Lampung.

2. ZERO INFLATED POISSON METHOD WITH A NEW MODIFIED BIAS ESTIMATOR

The Poisson distribution or Poisson random variable distribution, describes the number of "successes" that occur within a certain area or time interval. The random variable Y represents the number of events in a Poisson experiment and is called a Poisson random variable, while the Poisson distribution refers to the probability distribution that describes the likelihood of specific values of this random variable occurring. Poisson distribution has the following random variable probability function Y [6]:

$$p(y; \mu) = \frac{e^{-\mu} \mu^y}{y!} \quad (1)$$

In Poisson distribution, the mean value and the variance value have the same value as $E(Y) = Var(Y) = \mu$. In finding out whether the data used

comes from Poisson distribution, it can be done by the Chi-Square test. With the test statistics used:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i} \quad (2)$$

Poisson regression is used to analyze count data. Poisson regression is a standard model for discrete

data and belongs to the non-linear regression model. The Poisson regression model is [8]:

$$y_i = \mu_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (3)$$

$$\mu_i = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \beta_2 x_{2i} + \dots + \beta_p) \quad (4)$$

In estimating parameters in the Poisson regression model using the MLE method, the main objective is to maximize the likelihood function based on the known distribution of the model. This process produces the Maximum Likelihood estimator, which is expressed as $\hat{\beta}_{ML} = [X^T \widehat{W} X]^{-1} X^T \widehat{W} \hat{s}$. The partial

parameter significance test is used to determine whether each parameter in the regression model has a significant effect on the response variable, considering the presence of other parameters. One test that is often used to test the significance of partial parameters is the Wald test, which has a related test statistic [5]:

$$W_j = \left(\frac{\hat{\beta}_j}{SE(\hat{\beta}_j)} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

In addition to the partial parameter significance test in Poisson regression, there is also a simultaneous parameter test used to test whether all parameters in the regression model simultaneously have a

$$G = -2 \ln(L_0 - L_1) \tag{6}$$

The determination coefficient (R^2) is the amount of diversity of response variables described or explained by the predictor variable. The value of R^2 ranges from 0 to 1. There are 3 types of Pseudo R Square used in this study, namely: Cox and Snell R Square, Nagelkerke R Square, and Mc Fadden's.

2.1 Zero Inflated Poisson Regression

In Poisson regression models, count data often

$$P(Y = y_i) = \begin{cases} \omega_i + (1 - \omega_i)e^{-\mu_i}, & \text{untuk } y_i = 0 \\ \frac{(1 - \omega_i)e^{-\mu_i}\mu_i^{y_i}}{y_i!}, & \text{untuk } y_i > 0 \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

Where $\mu_i \leq 0$ and $0 \leq \omega_i \leq 1$. The mean of the ZIP and the variance is given as $E(Y_i) = \mu_i$ and

$Var(Y_i) = \mu_i + \frac{\omega}{1-\omega}\mu_i^2$. States the linking model, as [9]:

$$\ln(\mu) = X_i^T \beta \tag{8}$$

$$\text{logit}(\omega) = \ln \left[\frac{\omega}{1-\omega} \right] = X_i^T \gamma \tag{9}$$

2.2 Poisson Ridge Regression

In Poisson regression, multicollinearity can cause instability and imprecision in the estimation of regression coefficients. Multicollinearity can occur when two or more independent variables are highly

correlated with each other in the regression model. Multicollinearity testing in regression models can be seen from the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value. With the VIF formula as follows:

$$VIF = \frac{1}{1 - R_j^2} \tag{10}$$

Multicollinearity problems require special handling so that the model can provide valid results. One approach to overcome multicollinearity is to use ridge regression. Poisson Ridge Regression (PRR) combines the concepts of Poisson regression and ridge regression. The main objective of PRR is to model count data by reducing overfitting and overcoming multicollinearity problems by applying

the ridge method to the Poisson model. In the multicollinearity problem, this can be overcome by adding a bias rule k so that it can reduce the value of the estimated variance compared to the estimated variance in Poisson regression. In Ridge Poisson regression, transformation or standardization is first carried out by centering and scaling methods, which aim to overcome data that has different units. The

formula for standardizing centering and scaling is [10]:

$$X_{ij}^* = \frac{X_{ij} - \bar{X}_j}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_{ij} - \bar{X}_j)^2}} \quad (11)$$

In applying the PPR method, the principle that the Maximum Likelihood estimates the minimum Weight Sum of Square Error (WSSE) is used. The $\hat{\beta}_{ML}$ estimator obtained will be seen as the optimal estimator in WSSE. Suppose \hat{B} is chosen in addition to $\hat{\beta}_{ML}$ where \hat{B} is a vector estimator of a vector of β

so that the WSSE of the estimator can be written from the estimator is $\phi = \phi_{min} + \phi(\hat{B})$. To obtain the parameter estimation value in PRR is done by minimizing the Lagrange function using $\hat{B}^T \hat{B}$ with $\phi(\hat{B}) = \phi_0$ which can be written based on the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(\hat{B}) &= \phi_0 \\ (\hat{B} - \hat{\beta}_{ML})^T X^T \hat{W} X (\hat{B} - \hat{\beta}_{ML}) &= \phi_0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Then it is done in the form of Lagrangian as in the equation below.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min } F &= \hat{B}^T \hat{B} + \frac{1}{k} \left((\hat{B} - \hat{\beta}_{ML})^T X^T \hat{W} X (\hat{B} - \hat{\beta}_{ML} - \phi_0) \right) \\ &= \hat{B}^T \hat{B} + \frac{1}{k} \left(\hat{B}^T X^T \hat{W} X \hat{B} - \hat{\beta}_{ML}^T X^T \hat{W} X \hat{B} - X^T \hat{W} X \hat{B}^T \hat{\beta}_{ML} + \hat{\beta}_{ML}^T X^T \hat{W} X \hat{\beta}_{ML} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \phi_0 \right) \\ &= \hat{B}^T \hat{B} + \frac{1}{k} \left(\hat{B}^T X^T \hat{W} X \hat{B} - 2 \hat{B}^T X^T \hat{W} X \hat{\beta}_{ML} + \hat{\beta}_{ML}^T X^T \hat{W} X \hat{\beta}_{ML} - \phi_0 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

with $\frac{1}{k}$ is multiple Lagrange and ϕ_0 is number of squared errors. After that, the above equation is

derived from \hat{B} with the result equalized to zero, so that the equation of the PRR method is :

$$\hat{\beta}_{PRR} = (kI + X^T \hat{W} X)^{-1} X^T \hat{W} \hat{S} \quad (14)$$

2.3 Zero Inflated Poisson Ridge Regression

Zero Inflated Poisson Ridge Regression (ZIPRR) is a model developed to handle multicollinearity in ZIP. The ZIP model is widely used for caught data that has an excess of zero, but multicollinearity can cause regression estimates to be unstable and inaccurate. ZIPRR aims to improve the stability and accuracy of the regression coefficient estimation in the Zero Inflated Poisson model by reducing the

variance of the estimator and optimizing the estimation to achieve the optimal MSE value.

Under the condition of multicollinearity, the $X^T \hat{W} X$ matrix becomes poorly conditioned, resulting in high variance and instability of the MLE estimator at Zero Inflated Poisson. To address this issue:

$$\hat{\beta}_{ZIPRR} = (kI + X^T \hat{W} X)^{-1} X^T \hat{W} X \hat{\beta}_{ML} = C \hat{\beta}_{ML} \quad (15)$$

Where $k > 0$. Mean and variance of Zero Inflated Poisson Ridge Regression [11]:

$$E[\hat{\beta}_{ZIPRR}] = (C - I)\beta \text{ and } \text{var}[\hat{\beta}_{ZIPRR}] = C(X^T \hat{W} X)^{-1} C^T \quad (16)$$

2.4 New Modified Ridge k Parameters

In Zero Inflated Poisson regression to handle the multicollinearity problem in the data, an appropriate estimator is needed to overcome the problem. New Modified Ridge Parameters (NMRP) was developed to improve the accuracy of parameter estimation in the ZIP model by modifying the applied (k) estimator. In a recent study, a modified ridge-based

estimator for Zero Inflated Poisson regression model was developed [7]. Estimator k aims to reduce the effect of multicollinearity by using a ridge regression approach in a more optimized ZIP model and improve the stability of the model under high multicollinearity conditions. The following three estimators are used to solve the multicollinearity problem in Zero Inflated Poisson regression:

$$\widehat{k}_1 = \max \left\{ \frac{\lambda}{(n-p) + \lambda \hat{\alpha}^2} \right\} \quad (17)$$

$$\widehat{k}_2 = \text{median} \left\{ \frac{\lambda}{(n-p) + \lambda \hat{\alpha}^2} \right\} \quad (18)$$

$$\widehat{k}_3 = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{\lambda}{(n-p) + \lambda \hat{\alpha}^2} \quad (19)$$

These three estimators are designed to optimize parameter estimates by reducing bias due to multicollinearity without removing important information from the data. Where λ is the eigenvalue $X^T \widehat{W} X$ and $\hat{\alpha}^2$ is the value $\delta^T \beta_{ML}$, with δ^T is the eigenvector element of the matrix $X^T \widehat{W} X$.

3. METHODOLOGY

The data used in this study are secondary data obtained from the Bandar Lampung City Health Office Profile in 2021 <https://www.dinkeskotabalam.com>. The response variable (Y) used in this study is the number of Tetanus Neonatorum cases in each health center in Bandar Lampung City, Lampung. The predictor variables (X) used are 4 variables with the percentage of pregnant women examined (X_1) who were examined 4 times during pregnancy, the percentage of Tetanus Toxoid immunization in pregnant women (X_2), the percentage of maternity mothers assisted by health workers (X_3), and the percentage of neonatal examination (X_4) conducted 3 times at 6-48 hours of

age, 3-7 days of age and 8-28 days of age. The analysis for data on Tetanus Neonatorum cases in Bandar Lampung City, Lampung begins by testing whether the data follows a Poisson distribution or not using the Chi-Square test. Furthermore, it was tested whether the data had multicollinearity problems or not by looking at the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value. Then it is also tested whether the data has overdispersion or not by looking at the $E(Y)$ and $\text{Var}(Y)$ values. Finally, zero inflation will be checked by looking at the number of zero values in the response variable. Furthermore, the data is analyzed using Zero Inflated Poisson regression with MLE method and Zero Inflated Poisson with modified bias estimator. However, before modeling Zero Inflated Poisson with a modified biased estimator, first determine the Ridge penalty parameter k . In choosing the best model between Zero Inflated Poisson with MLE method and Zero Inflated Poisson with modified bias estimator, it is done by looking at the smallest MSE value, following the MSE formula used:

$$MSE = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\hat{Y}_t - Y_t)^2}{n}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (20)$$

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

It will be tested whether the data is distributed poisson or not using the Chi Square test, the hypothesis used is $H_0 =$ Data used Poisson

distribution vs $H_1 =$ Data used is not Poisson distribution with $\alpha = 0.05$, so that the value of $\chi^2_{(0.05,30)} = 43.77$ The results can be seen from Table 1.

Table 1: Poisson Distribution Test

N	31
p-value	0.4402
Chi Square count	1.6409

Based on Table 1, since the value of p-value = 0.4402 > $\alpha = 0.05$ or the value of Chi Square count = 1.6409 < $\chi^2_{(0.05,2)} = 5.991$, there is not enough evidence to reject H_0 . Since there is not enough evidence to refute H_0 , it can be concluded that the data spread along with Poisson distribution.

Multicollinearity testing will be carried out on Tetanus Neonatorum case data in the city of Bandar Lampung, Lampung. This test will be carried out by looking at the VIF value, if the VIF value is > 10, then there is a multicollinearity problem. The results of this test can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: VIF Value of Independent Variable

Variable	VIF
X_1	12.5400
X_2	4.0721
X_3	4.7722
X_4	18.8759

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the VIF value in variable $X_1 > 10$ is 12.5400 and in variable $X_4 > 10$ is 18.8759 so it can be concluded that the independent variable in the Tetanus Neonatorum data in the city of Bandar Lampung, Lampung detects multicollinearity.

The examination of overdispersion in the data of Tetanus Neonatorum cases in the city of Bandar Lampung, Lampung can be seen from the variant values and mean values of the response variables in the data. If the var value is $\text{var}(Y) > E(Y)$, the data indicates an overdispersion problem. The results of the overdispersion test can be seen from Table 3.

Table 3: Overdispersion Examination

Value	Y
Variance	1.1699
Mean	0.3548

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the value of $\text{Var}(Y) > E(Y)$ with the variance value in the response variable is 1.1699 and the mean value in the response variable is 0.3548. This indicates an overdispersion in the data. In addition to the overdispersion check

on the data, it is necessary to carry out a zero inflation check which can be seen from the large percentage of zero values in the response variables. The condition for zero inflation is a zero value in the response variable of more than 50%. The results of this examination can be seen in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Zero Inflation Examination on Response Variables

Many observations on the data	Many observations have zero values on the data	Percentage
31	27	87%

Based on Table 4, it can be seen that the percentage of zero values in the response variable is 87% so that it can be concluded that there is zero inflation in the response variable of the Tetanus Neonatorum Case

in the Tetanus Neonatorum data in the city of Bandar Lampung, Lampung. Next, a partial parameter significance test of the Poisson regression model is conducted to see the significance of each

independent variable that affects the dependent variable. The test statistics used in this test are the Wald test with the hypothesis $H_0:\beta_j = 0$ vs $H_1:\beta_j \neq 0$, as well as a significance level of 5%, so that the

value of $\chi^2_{(0.05,1)} = 3.841$. The results of the partial parameter significance test on the poisson regression model can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Partial Parameter Significance Test of Poisson Regression Model

Parameter	Guess Value	Standard Error	Wald Test Statistics	p-value
β_0	-128.199	64.210		
β_1	3.355	2.611	27.0983	1.934×10^{-7}
β_2	3.043	1.616	0.0378	0.8459
β_3	2.384	1.358	3.1966	0.0738
β_4	-6.873	3.218	11.3140	0.0008

From Table 5, it can be concluded that β_1 and β_4 are significant at a significance level of 5%. This means that the factors of examining pregnant women and the factors of examining neonates have a great influence on the case of Tetanus Neonatorum. There are two independent variables that affect the dependent variable according to the Wald test, so the Poisson regression model formed is $\hat{\mu} = \exp(-128.199 + 3.355X_1 - 6.873X_4)$. The model shows that Tetanus Neonatorum cases in Bandar Lampung, Indonesia are influenced by the percentage of pregnant women examined (X_1) and the percentage of neonatal examinations (X_4).

accuracy, especially in situations where excess zeros have a significant impact on the data distribution. However, the Zero Inflated Poisson model cannot overcome the multicollinearity problem that causes instability and inaccuracy in the estimation of the coefficients. and inaccuracies in the estimation of regression coefficients.. In dealing with data that has multicollinearity and overdispersion problems, the Zero Inflated Poisson (ZIP) model with New Modified Bias Estimator can be used. In using this model, it is done by determining some form of parameter ($k_1, k_2, \text{ and } k_3$). This estimator is designed to reduce the effects of multicollinearity with a more optimal Ridge regression approach, so as to optimize parameter estimates by reducing bias without eliminating important information in the data. The estimated parameters obtained are presented in Table 6.

The Zero Inflated Poisson regression model with Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) method offer better adjustability in capturing excess zeros in a more effective manner resulting in better model

Table 6: Estimator Value of Zero Inflated Poisson

Parameter	Method			
	MLE	$k_1 = 0.0085$	$k_2 = 0.0066$	$k_3 = 0.0056$
β_0	-24.142	0.3547	0.3548	0.3548
β_1	7.818	3.4255	3.4399	3.4477
β_4	-7.318	-1.2204	-1.2324	-1.2389
γ_0	160.7	0.9997	0.9998	0.9998
γ_1	156.6	-1.6707×10^{-17}	-1.3163×10^{-17}	-1.1243×10^{-17}
γ_4	-154.8	1.1283×10^{-18}	8.9065×10^{-18}	7.6148×10^{-18}

From Table 6, the values of each Zero Inflated Poisson parameter with the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) and New Modified Bias Estimator methods are obtained. To choose the best model, this

study uses the smallest Mean Squared Error (MSE) value. The MSE value for the Zero Inflated Poisson model with the MLE method and the New Modified Bias Estimator is obtained in Table 7.

Table 7: MSE Values of Zero Inflated Poisson

Method	MSE values
ZIP k_1	0.88200
ZIP k_2	0.88197
ZIP k_3	0.88196
ZIP MLE	75.56787

It can be seen in Table 7, the comparison of MSE values obtained in Zero Inflated Poisson using the k_1 ridge parameter value is 0.88200, in Zero Inflated Poisson using the ridge parameter value k_2 the MSE value is 0.88197, in Zero Inflated Poisson using the ridge parameter value k_3 the MSE value is 0.88196, finally in Zero Inflated Poisson using the MLE method the MSE value is 75.56787. From some of these methods, the smallest MSE value was obtained

in Zero Inflated Poisson using the value of the ridge parameter k_3 compared to other methods. Thus, the results were obtained that by using the new modified Zero Inflated Poisson bias estimator, Ridge k_3 better used in overcoming the problem of overdispersion and multicollinearity in the data of Tetanus Neonatorum cases in the city of Bandar Lampung, Lampung. With the new modified Zero Inflated Poisson model of the bias Ridge k_3 as follows:

$$\ln(\mu_{ZIP3}) = 0.3548 + 3.4477X_1 - 1.2389X_4$$

$$\text{logit}(\omega_{ZIP3}) = 0.9998 - (1.1243 \times 10^{-17})X_1 + (7.6148 \times 10^{-18})X_4$$

From the Zero Inflated Poisson model with a new modified bias estimator ridge k_3 shows that the incidence of Tetanus Neonatorum in Bandar Lampung, Indonesia are influenced by the percentage of pregnant women (X_1) and the percentage of neonatal examinations (X_4).

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, by comparing Zero Inflated Poisson with the MLE method and a new modified bias estimator values of Ridge k used in the Tetanus Neonatorum case data in the city of Bandar Lampung in 2021, it can be seen that the smallest MSE value can be used. The smallest MSE value was obtained in the Zero Inflated Poisson estimator with the Ridge k_3 parameter method of 0.88196. So that the best model on the Tetanus Neonatorum case data in the city of Bandar Lampung, Lampung to

overcome the problem of overdispersion and multicollinearity using the new Ridge k_3 modified bias estimator Zero Inflated Poisson. With the new modified Zero Inflated Poisson model of the bias Ridge k_3 as follows:

$$\ln(\mu_{ZIP3}) = 0.3548 + 3.4477X_1 - 1.2389X_4$$

$$\text{logit}(\omega_{ZIP3}) = 0.9998 - (1.1243 \times 10^{-17})X_1 + (7.6148 \times 10^{-18})X_4$$

From the Zero Inflated Poisson model with a new modified bias estimator ridge k_3 shows that the incidence of Tetanus Neonatorum in Bandar Lampung, Indonesia is influenced by the percentage of pregnant women examined (X_1) who were examined 4 times during pregnancy and the percentage of neonatal examination (X_4) conducted 3 times at 6-48 hours of age, 3-7 days of age and 8-28 days of age

REFERENCES

- [1] Aprilia, A.D. "Regresi Zero Inflated Poisson Pemodelan Angka Positif Penyakit Malaria di Jawa Timur," *Jurnal Ilmiah Matematika*, XI (2), pp. 139-146, 2023.
- [2] Famoye, F., & Singh, K.P. "Zero-Inflated Generalized Poisson Regression Model with an Application to Domestic Violence Data," *Journal of Data Science*, IV (1), pp. 117-130, 2006.
- [3] Herawati, N., Fitriyani, A., Saidi, S., & Setiawan, E. "Overdispersion Data Modeling Cases of Filariasis in East Lampung Province, Indonesia," *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, VIII (6), pp. 31-39, 2023.
- [4] Herawati, N., Sukma, H.J., Nisa, K., Nusyirwan, Saidi, S., Tiryono, & Misgiyati. "Poisson Ridge Regression for Multicollinearity Data: Case Study of the Number of Maternal Deaths In Lampung Province, Lampung," *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, XIII (1), pp. 1-8, 2024.
- [5] Lambert, D. "Zero-Inflated Poisson Regression with an Application to Defects in Manufacturing," *Journal Technometrics*, XXXIV (1), pp. 1-14, 1992.
- [6] Walpole, R.E. *Pengantar Statistika*, PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta, 1995.
- [7] Zeeshan, M., Khan, A., Amanullah M., Bakr, M.E., Alshangiti A.M., Bologun, O.S., & Yusuf, M. "A New Modified Biased Estimator for Zero Inflated Poisson Regression Model," *Journal Heliyon*, X (1), pp. 1-8, 2024.
- [8] Myres, R.H. *Classical and Modern Regression with Applications*. 2nd Edition, PWS-KENT Publishing Company, Boston, 1990.
- [9] Jansakul, N. & Hinde, J.P. "Score Test for Zero-Inflated Models," *Journal Computational Statistics and Data Analysis*, XL (1), pp. 75-96, 2002.
- [10] Marx, B. & Smith, E.P. "Weighted Multicollinearity in Logistic Regression," *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Science*. XLVII (5), pp. 1128-1135, 1990.
- [11] Younus, F.A.G., Othman, R.A., & Algamal, Z.Y. "Modified Ridge Estimator in Zero Inflated Poisson Regression Model," *Int. J. Agricult. Stat. Sci.* XVIII (1), pp. 1245-1250, 2022.